

COVERAGE OF WAR PARTICIPANTS' ADDRESSES IN ARCHIVED DOCUMENTS

Ibadullayeva Gulhayo Shuxrat qizi

Intern researcher at the Institute of History

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ABSTRACT

This article was written using the letters received by the citizens of the newspapers, kept in the National Archives of Uzbekistan¹.

In the Second World War of 1941-1945, the multi-ethnic people of Uzbekistan showed great courage and fortitude on the battlefields and behind the front, making a worthy contribution to ensuring the victory over fascism. Of the more than 1.5 million Uzbeks who took part in the war, more than half a million died, about 133 thousand went missing, and more than 60 thousand returned disabled.

During that extremely difficult and turbulent period, our country became a strong supply base for the front, the industrial enterprises here were adapted to the military sector, and their activities were directed to the needs of the front. Our citizens have mobilized all their strength and capabilities to restore more than a hundred factories and factories that were evacuated to Uzbekistan.

More than 1 million people were relocated to our country from the regions that were caught in the flames of war. 200 thousand of them were children. Our people gave them shelter, shared their last bread, brought up children who were separated from their parents as their own children, and demonstrated their true humanitarian qualities to the whole world.

Unfortunately, a complete scientific-historical book or collection of documents that comprehensively reflects the difficult and difficult life of the people of Uzbekistan at the front and behind the front during this bloody war, and their great contribution to the victory over fascism. not yet created. Such sources are extremely important in terms of conveying the great deeds done by our people during the war years, their strong will and heroism, the reality of that time to future generations based on concrete examples, and educating them in the spirit of patriotism and courage.

¹ O`zbekiston Milliy Arxivi. P-2806 fond Ro`znomalar taxririyatiga fuqarolardan tushgan maktublar to`plami. Ro`yhat № 1.

Taking into account the worthy contribution of our nation to the great victory achieved in the Second World War of 1941-1945, a number of events are being implemented in order to reward the war participants and provide them with financial support for their bravery, as well as the reconstruction of our nation. reflects the political, economic, material and spiritual life of the period. Through the letters, we can see the meetings with the mature people of our time, their memoirs, the attitude of the population towards the important events, and also in the appeals received from the citizens. In particular, among the many collections of the Central State Archive of the Republic of Uzbekistan 1.1. in the process of reading the letters from the articles, the opinions and comments expressed from the articles printed on the pages of the newspaper "Soviet Uzbekistan" were found in handwritten and typewritten letters.

As an example, Uz. SSR. Tashkent albasti Ordjokidze r.n., p.o. Argen ul. Djoldibekov Soyilbek Islamovich, a resident of Sentralnaya 316, complained that awards were distributed by state organizations on the occasion of the 40th anniversary of the Great Victory on May 9, but he was not given any awards even though he participated in the war and returned as a disabled person of the 1st group², on 25.05.1985. sent a letter.

Andijan region, Khojaabad district. Q/z. R. Sultanov, a resident of Leninchi address, was dissatisfied with the activities of the district head V. S. Shokhin, and the state organizations distributed awards on the occasion of the 40th anniversary of the great victory on May 9, but despite his contribution to the great victory, he was still awarded the appeal sent by the activists of the local neighborhood complaining about the fact that it was not mentioned even once (13.06.1985)³.

By the early 1990s, similar appeals were heavily criticized by the public. Thus, letters are often used in historical research and serve as important additions to the study of biographies, especially major political figures, sources for the study of the history of everyday life of an ordinary person, sometimes not recorded by researchers and there will only be "competitors" of normal conversations that have been revived., for example, through memories. The epistolary genre, which includes writings, is the most attractive for analysis within the framework of anthropological history, social history, etc. It would not be an exaggeration to say that in the course of reading the letters with such a content, the lack of attention to our compatriots, who made a worthy contribution to the great victory achieved in the Second World War, was clearly felt in the citizens' discontent and their moods.

On all fronts of the 1941-1945 war, Uzbek fighters showed miracles of heroism and bravery. The Second World War showed that Turkestan fighters, including Uzbeks, had preserved traditional war skills on all fronts. In total, 1,433,230 people from Uzbekistan were mobilized for World War II. This was 50-60 percent of the population fit for war in Uzbekistan at that time. Uzbeks made up the majority of the Soviet soldiers serving in the border troops.

The bravery of Uzbeks such as Lieutenant Usov, political leader Sharipov near Grodno, Akhmed Aliev, Daniyor Abdullaev, Bobokomil Kashanov, Uzog Otaev, Madamin Khojiev in the

² O`zbekiston Milliy Arxivi. P-2806 fond Ro`znomalar taxririya-tiga fuqarolardan tushgan maktublar to`plami. Ro`yhat No1, 25.05.1985

³ O`zbekiston Milliy Arxivi. P-2806 fond Ro`znomalar taxririya-tiga fuqarolardan tushgan maktublar to`plami. Ro`yhat No1 (13.06.1985);

defense of the Brest Fortress became a symbol of the heroic courage of the defenders of Uzbekistan, while repelling the enemy attack on the outskirts of Moscow under the command of Major General Panfilov the division showed especially tenacity, 180 commanders who graduated from the Tashkent Infantry School fought in the ranks of this division. Among them were I. Jalilov, M. Madaminov, A. Togaev and others.

During the battles for the Caucasus, the division under the command of Sabir Rahimov, formed in Tashkent, received an order from the high command to stop the advance of the enemy in one of the important parts of the front. S. Rahimov's division killed 8,000 soldiers and officers of the enemy in long-lasting battles. Later, General S. Rahimov traveled the glorious battle route from the Caucasus to East Prussia. Sabir Rahimov was killed in the battles for the city of Gdańsk. The battery under the command of Uzbek boy Botir Boboev was one of the first to cross the Oder river on the way to Berlin and destroyed the enemy. For this bravery, B. Boboev was awarded the title of Hero.

The name of Mamadali Topiboldiev, a brave intelligence officer who fought against the Nazis and was awarded the title of Hero, is famous in Belarus. He killed 67 enemy soldiers and officers and captured 180 people. More than 120,000 young men and women from Uzbekistan were awarded combat orders and medals, and 338 people were awarded the title of Hero for their bravery and fortitude on the war fronts. 32 Uzbek soldiers were awarded the Order of Glory of three levels.

Due to the selfless efforts of our people and the heroic courage of our fighters, the long-lasting war against the German-Nazi invaders ended with victory. On the night of August 9, 1945, the Soviet government started a war against Japan due to the agreement with the Allied countries and the danger in the East. 6,770 Uzbek fighters participated in this battle, which lasted until September 2, and defeated the Kwantung army. During the surrender of Japan, many compatriots such as N. Latipov, A. Karimov, U. Doniyorov showed high military skill and combat activity.

Even at the cost of great sacrifices, Uzbeks made a worthy contribution to saving humanity from the scourge of fascism. "Remembrance" books were compiled in order to restore and value the memory of those who died in the war, the Memorial Square and the monument to the bereaved mother were restored in the center of our capital, and May 9 was declared the "Remembrance and Appreciation" day.

As it is known, today, the incomparable contribution of the multinational people of Uzbekistan to the Great Victory over fascism in the Second World War is to be deeply studied and promoted in every way, to always remember and perpetuate the memory of our brave and courageous ancestors who sacrificed their lives for the freedom of the Motherland, the war that is becoming a blessing in our ranks today. and in recent years, great work has been done in our country to show great respect to veterans of the labor front, to improve their health, living conditions, and material support⁴.

In particular, previously closed archive funds are being opened, cooperation with the former Union republics and foreign countries is being strengthened in this direction, new

⁴ Мирзиёев Ш.М. Буюк келажигимизни мард ва олижаноб халкимиз билан бирга курамыз. - Тошкент: Узбекистон, 2017. 12,14. bet

information about the contribution of our people to the Great Victory, the heroism of our ancestors during the war years is being revealed and presented to our people.

An effective system has been formed in our country to repair the homes of war and labor veterans, improve their living conditions, provide them with patronage services, and provide them with rest in sanatoriums.

Especially, on the eve of the Day of Remembrance and Appreciation, it has become a noble tradition to present congratulatory letters, monetary awards and valuable gifts to war and labor veterans on behalf of the President, to organize meetings dedicated to their bravery, to perform in mass media, to prepare books, albums, movies, and stage plays.

As a practical confirmation of these ideas and in order to show greater respect to the representatives of the older generation who have been making a worthy contribution to the comprehensive development of Uzbekistan, to the education of young people in the spirit of patriotism, and to strengthen the social protection of war and labor veterans, another important document - the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan "The Second World War" "On measures to further strengthen the material support of the participants in the war" was adopted.

In accordance with the decree, the minimum pension amount is set for the participants of the Second World War, as well as those who were held captive in Nazi concentration camps as minors and who worked in the siege of Leningrad⁵.

There is no doubt that this Decree is another great example of the great attention and care shown by our state and society to our brave and brave compatriots who saved our people and the whole humanity from the scourge of fascism, and it is to further appreciate the fighting activities and selfless work of our heroic ancestors for today's peaceful and free life. and honoring, serves to educate our youth to be healthy and mature people in the spirit of their glorious traditions.

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⁵ Мирзиёев Ш.М. Конун устуворлиги ва инсон манфаатларини таъминлаш юрт тараккиёти ва халк фаровонлигининг гарови. - Тошкент: Узбекистон, 2017.

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